

"ANIMAL" THEME REFLECTED IN FOLKLORE

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Annotation

This article talks about the unit of linguoculturalism known as the paremiological fund of the language. As an example, Uzbek and Turkish proverbs involving kelsemas related to animals were used. The meanings of lexemes are mentioned. The content of proverbs is explained.

Key words: phomene, discourse, lexeme, sema, paremiological background, symbol, positive color, content plan, vocabulary.

Linguistics is a science that studies language as a cultural phenomenon, and language and culture in interaction form its subject. [2;21] The subject of linguistic culture is the linguistic units that have acquired a symbolic, figurative, metaphorical meaning in culture, and the results of which are summarized in the human mind and reflected in myths, legends, folklore and religious discourses, poetic and prosaic artistic texts, phraseology, metaphors and symbols. 2;27] One of the lingucultural units is the paremeological (proverbs and proverbs) fund of the language. The paremiological fund of the language can be called a jewel box made up of national masterpieces and firmly rooted in its culture. It is known that the original meaning of the proverb is "small work, speech". According to the dictionary, it is written: "A concise, figurative, full-meaning wise phrase, sentence, created by the people on the basis of life experience, usually with the content of advice." [3;665] As V. N. Teliya said, linguocultural science primarily studies the living communicative processes and the connection of the language expressions used in them with the mentality of the people

in synchronic movement. the experiences and imaginations of our ancestors are sealed. Researching the symbols expressed in them and their correct interpretation serve to illuminate the inner world of our ancestors, bring us closer to them, and enrich our spirituality. Therefore, we will analyze lexemes related to the type of animals used in several Uzbek and Turkish proverbs.

Even a dead lion makes a horse growl.

The gaze of the brave is sharper than the sword of the coward.[4;91]

The proverbs given as examples are also synonymous. Let's dwell on the lexeme of the lion, which is a symbol of strength and courage in Turks. The lion is made of marble or wood and is placed at the entrance of the palace or mausoleum. This image means that the Turkic country is always on the defensive. [6;61] In the culture of most peoples, it is a symbol of power, power, kingdom, and the king of animals. On the other hand, it shows impudence, savagery, animal lifestyle. [2; 146] So, the lexeme lion consists of symbols of hero, brave, fearless, strong. The content plan of the proverb is to say: "A coward, a "heartless" person is a brave, courageous, brave, fearless person who is afraid even of death."

A horse is a wing of a young man

A horse is a friend of the herd. [4;88]

In the following Uzbek and Turkish proverbs, both the meaning and the lexeme reflecting the content of the proverb are common. A horse is a strong, patient, handsome, clean, intelligent, alert animal with a strong ability to immediately notice, see, smell, hear and sense sounds, even unknown ghosts. In addition to these qualities, the horse is a wonderful animal that is a faithful friend, a faithful friend, a helper in difficult tasks, a companion on trips, and often saves a person from death in battles and other dangerous situations.[7;263] In the ancient Turks, the horse was considered a lucky animal. It is imagined that he is a constant companion of a person, equal to a person in terms of status, born on the same day. [6;119] According to Mahmud Koshgari, the horse is "the wing of the Turk". According to scientific data, horses were

domesticated approximately three thousand years before Christ. So, the noun lexeme summarizes the concepts that have a number of positive connotations in its composition, i.e. strong, pure, intelligent, faithful, loyal. Variants of this proverb: "If you have a horse, you have wings"; "Shoot - your wings"; "The wing of the earth is a horse"; "the horse is finished - the wing is finished" ; Such as "The horse touched - the wing touched". There are a lot of proverbs in Uzbek and Turkish folklore with the noun lexeme. Another example:

The death of a horse is a holiday of a dog

A horse's death is a dog's holiday. [4;80]

These proverbs also express a general meaning. By the given example, it is possible to make sure that the noun lexeme has positive connotations. "The horse is one of the totem animals in the Turkic tribes, and as a spirit of goodness, it helps the shaman to win over the spirit of evil. The shaman's staffs often represent the symbol of a horse, and the Uzbek people still believe that the horse has a demon. Since Uzbeks and Turks are brotherly peoples from ancient times, the lexemes used in proverbs, which have been preserved for centuries, are common. The noun lexeme used in both proverbs reflected a positive color. In the case of the dog lexeme, it represented a negative color in both paremiological units. In Uzbeks, Turks and a number of other Turkic peoples, a dog means insult. [2;43] Variants of the proverb: "The death of a horse is a wedding to a dog"; "If the donkey dies - marry the dog." Content: "The death, defeat, and failure of good people makes bad and depressed people happy. Even if they see some material or spiritual benefit due to this event, they will still be happy. Because that's the nature of black people." [5;313] It should be mentioned here that the lexeme dog does not always reflect negative meanings. Russians associate the dog with negativity as well as loyalty, loyalty, simplicity. [2;43]

In short, proverbs belonging to the folk art have a whole world of meaning in their core. In particular, Uzbek and Turkish proverbs have many common aspects. The lexemes denoting the type of animal used in them have expressed their original meaning in different places. Lexemes with positive and negative colors reflect the

content of the proverb. It is through the lexemes belonging to the animal species that people's character and characteristics are highlighted.

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